

Low overhead optimal parity codes

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ABSTRACT

The error detecting and correcting codes are used in critical applications like in intensive care units, defense applications, and require highly reliable data. This brief focuses on codes to detect and correct adjacent errors within a single clock cycle by using modulo-2 addition of data bits for parity generation, syndrome calculation, error location identification and correction by improving code rate and minimizing bit overhead. The optimal parity codes devised can correct odd number of adjacent errors upto $(N/2)-1$ data bits when compared with the existing codes with less delay. Four optimal codes are proposed using existing decimal matrix codes properties. The proposed codes prove better in terms of area, delay, power, bit overhead, code rate, code efficiency, and with good reliability. The components are developed in veriloghardware description language and verified for zynq 7000 series field programmable gate array in xilinx integrated synthesis environment 14.5 Tool. Among the codes devised, optimal code-4 proves to be a better code with 65.3% code rate and 53.12% bit overhead. Also when compared with other codes, it uses 33.3% less area and 1.89% less power delay product for encoder and 32.2% less area and 0.36% power delay product for decoder respectively.

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1. INTRODUCTION

In the applications like intensive care units where continuous evaluation and back up of data extracted from monitoring devices is required for patients, fast and reliable error detecting and correcting codes have attracted research [1]-[4]. Even in military applications, the backup data is usually necessary for missile launch and guidance [5]-[8]. This attracted a great attention for reliable codes capable of operating at high frequencies [9]-[12].

The recent developments and advanced research at various levels of abstraction induced hope of using very small area specifically allocated in each embedded memory [13]-[15] with built-in self test capability [16]-[19]. But the promising future of electronics at nanoscale allows the devices get closer where the devices undergo radiation effects giving rise to multiple event upsets that induce soft errors in memories [20]-[23]. For embedded memories, the correction capability must be as high as possible within a single clock cycle to ensure at-speed testing [24]-[28]. This paper addresses the correction of maximum number of erroneous bits as fast as possible by using minimum number of redundant bits and maximum code rate.

The basic error detection and correction codes utilize the various blocks as shown in Figure 1. The encoder uses two step processes i.e., the horizontal vector hamming code encoding and the discussed encoders to generate code word. This code word is written into the memory [29], [30]. Using read operation,

the data is decoded first by horizontal vector hamming code decoder and later by parity decoder which verify the parity bits for correcting detected errors. The entire process of error detection and correction is based on Hamming codes for all the existing or proposed parity codes [29], [30].

Figure 1. Error detection and correction process

Majorly the changes are incorporated in parity encoder and decoder blocks for error detection and correction codes. The additional bits required depends on type of method adopted in encoder on the basis of hamming distance which aid in the development of code word that is written into memory. To obtain efficient error detection and correction codes, the decoder block is optimized with respect to area, delay, and power, this paper proposes four new codes, as matrix codes are quite faster than other codes and are easy to incorporate for memory. In this paper, the process represented in Figure 1 is used and the codes either existing or proposed are used in the place of parity encoder and decoder blocks only. The paper is structured as the accessible codes in section 2 which prove to correct a maximum of 32 adjacent bits but use large number of parity bits with less code rate. To overcome this, the proposed error detection and correction codes i.e., the proposed solution as four optimal parity codes in section 3 are discussed. The section 4 deals with simulation results and comparison in terms of assessed parameters followed by conclusion.

2. METHOD

The method adopted is represented in two sections 2.1 as accessible codes which describe the mechanism of encoding and decoding adopted for proposed codes. Also the proposed codes are described in section 2.2 which are optimised for less number of parity bits. Further the designs are considered for evaluating technological parameters such as area, power and delay, nontechnological parameters such as code rate and bit overhead.

2.1. Accessible error detection and correction codes

In prose, several error detection and correction codes are projected, among them the easiest way of correcting errors is done by treating data to be written into memory as matrix and developing the redundant bits. Usually the data along with parity bits is written into memory and later extracted from memory by read operation [29]. The [2] uses the H, V, and D-Bits i.e., the horizontal, vertical and diagonal redundant bits respectively as in 3D parity codes [8]. Figure 2 represents 64-bit data in the form of matrix with 8 rows × 8 columns giving rise to 8-H, 8-V and 15-D Bits. These parity bits are developed by modulo-2 additions of data bits read from memory. In the decoder, if an error exists, then the combination of all H, V, and D Bits indicate the location where the data bit is corrected by flipping it. Hence usually decoder requires a complex circuit when compared to encoder. The D bits are used for location of error exactly in the memory. The deviation in H bits decides the existence of errors and the V bits indicate the maximum number of adjacent bits that are correctable for the given data by using ultrafast decoding scheme [6], [7] for a correction capability of maximum of 8 adjacent bits out of 64-data bits. Say if m₂₉ is erroneous, then it is reflected in h₄, v₆, and d₆ bits which deviate from the actual encoded parity bits, by using syndrome bits the data are corrected.

	V ₁	V ₂	V ₃	V ₄	V ₅	V ₆	V ₇	V ₈	
h ₁	m ₀	m ₁	m ₂	m ₃	m ₄	m ₅	m ₆	m ₇	
h ₂	m ₈	m ₉	m ₁₀	m ₁₁	m ₁₂	m ₁₃	m ₁₄	m ₁₅	d ₁
h ₃	m ₁₆	m ₁₇	m ₁₈	m ₁₉	m ₂₀	m ₂₁	m ₂₂	m ₂₃	d ₂
h ₄	m ₂₄	m ₂₅	m ₂₆	m ₂₇	m ₂₈	m ₂₉	m ₃₀	m ₃₁	d ₃
h ₅	m ₃₂	m ₃₃	m ₃₄	m ₃₅	m ₃₆	m ₃₇	m ₃₈	m ₃₉	d ₄
h ₆	m ₄₀	m ₄₁	m ₄₂	m ₄₃	m ₄₄	m ₄₅	m ₄₆	m ₄₇	d ₅
h ₇	m ₄₈	m ₄₉	m ₅₀	m ₅₁	m ₅₂	m ₅₃	m ₅₄	m ₅₅	d ₆
h ₈	m ₅₆	m ₅₇	m ₅₈	m ₅₉	m ₆₀	m ₆₁	m ₆₂	m ₆₃	d ₇
		d ₁₅	d ₁₄	d ₁₃	d ₁₂	d ₁₁	d ₁₀	d ₉	d ₈

Figure 2. 3D parity check code (8×8 matrix arrangement)

Neelima and Subhas [3], the existing 8×8 matrix representation is changed to 4×16 matrix representation by using matrix reordering technique to enable the consideration of 16 bits at a time for processing of data. The 4×16 matrix uses 39 redundant bits i.e., 4 H bits, 16 V bits, and 19 D bits. From Figure 3, say if m29 is erroneous, then it is reflected in h2, v14 and d4 parity bits which after comparison with the encoded parity bits corrected by using syndrome bits, for a correction capability of maximum of 16 adjacent bits for 64-data bits.

	V ₁	V ₂	V ₃	V ₄	V ₅	V ₆	V ₇	V ₈	V ₉	V ₁₀	V ₁₁	V ₁₂	V ₁₃	V ₁₄	V ₁₅	V ₁₆	
h ₁	m ₀	m ₁	m ₂	m ₃	m ₄	m ₅	m ₆	m ₇	m ₈	m ₉	m ₁₀	m ₁₁	m ₁₂	m ₁₃	m ₁₄	m ₁₅	
h ₂	m ₁₆	m ₁₇	m ₁₈	m ₁₉	m ₂₀	m ₂₁	m ₂₂	m ₂₃	m ₂₄	m ₂₅	m ₂₆	m ₂₇	m ₂₈	m ₂₉	m ₃₀	m ₃₁	d ₁
h ₃	m ₃₂	m ₃₃	m ₃₄	m ₃₅	m ₃₆	m ₃₇	m ₃₈	m ₃₉	m ₄₀	m ₄₁	m ₄₂	m ₄₃	m ₄₄	m ₄₅	m ₄₆	m ₄₇	d ₂
h ₄	m ₄₈	m ₄₉	m ₅₀	m ₅₁	m ₅₂	m ₅₃	m ₅₄	m ₅₅	m ₅₆	m ₅₇	m ₅₈	m ₅₉	m ₆₀	m ₆₁	m ₆₂	m ₆₃	d ₃
	d ₁₉	d ₁₈	d ₁₇	d ₁₆	d ₁₅	d ₁₄	d ₁₃	d ₁₂	d ₁₁	d ₁₀	d ₉	d ₈	d ₇	d ₆	d ₅	d ₄	

Figure 3. 3D parity check code (4×16 matrix arrangement)

	V ₁	V ₂	V ₃	V ₄	V ₅	V ₆	V ₇	V ₈	V ₉	V ₁₀	V ₁₁	V ₁₂	V ₁₃	V ₁₄	V ₁₅	V ₁₆	V ₁₇	V ₁₈	V ₁₉	V ₂₀	V ₂₁	V ₂₂	V ₂₃	V ₂₄	V ₂₅	V ₂₆	V ₂₇	V ₂₈	V ₂₉	V ₃₀	V ₃₁	V ₃₂	
h ₁	m ₀	m ₁	m ₂	m ₃	m ₄	m ₅	m ₆	m ₇	m ₈	m ₉	m ₁₀	m ₁₁	m ₁₂	m ₁₃	m ₁₄	m ₁₅	m ₁₆	m ₁₇	m ₁₈	m ₁₉	m ₂₀	m ₂₁	m ₂₂	m ₂₃	m ₂₄	m ₂₅	m ₂₆	m ₂₇	m ₂₈	m ₂₉	m ₃₀	m ₃₁	
h ₂	m ₃₂	m ₃₃	m ₃₄	m ₃₅	m ₃₆	m ₃₇	m ₃₈	m ₃₉	m ₄₀	m ₄₁	m ₄₂	m ₄₃	m ₄₄	m ₄₅	m ₄₆	m ₄₇	m ₄₈	m ₄₉	m ₅₀	m ₅₁	m ₅₂	m ₅₃	m ₅₄	m ₅₅	m ₅₆	m ₅₇	m ₅₈	m ₅₉	m ₆₀	m ₆₁	m ₆₂	m ₆₃	d ₁
	d ₃₃	d ₃₂	d ₃₁	d ₃₀	d ₂₉	d ₂₈	d ₂₇	d ₂₆	d ₂₅	d ₂₄	d ₂₃	d ₂₂	d ₂₁	d ₂₀	d ₁₉	d ₁₈	d ₁₇	d ₁₆	d ₁₅	d ₁₄	d ₁₃	d ₁₂	d ₁₁	d ₁₀	d ₉	d ₈	d ₇	d ₆	d ₅	d ₄	d ₃	d ₂	

Figure 4. 3D parity check code (2×32 matrix arrangement)

In Figure 4, the 2×32 matrix uses 67 parity bits i.e., 2 H bits, 32 V bits and 33D bits for 3D parity encoder. Say if m29 is erroneous, then it is reflected in h1, v30, and d3 bits which after comparison with the original redundant bits, is flipped for correct data output, for a correction capability of maximum of 32 adjacent errors for 64-bit data. In [4], a similar concept with H, V, forward and backward diagonal parity bits which increases the number of parity bits and requires a complex decoder for identification of candidate bit for a correction capability of maximum of 3 adjacent bits for 32-data bits. In [5], multidirectional parity code, similar to 3D codes uses syndrome for correction, thus reducing the decoder complexity comparatively for a correction capability of maximum of 7 adjacent bits for 32-data bits. In [6], horizontal vertical double diagonal parity code requires few refinement steps to be added to identify the candidate bits but still adds complexity in decoding process due to additional refinement steps, for a correction capability of maximum of 3 adjacent bits for 32-data bits.

2.2. Optimal error detection and correction codes

The matrix codes can be optimized by using minimal number of parity bits for a 2×32 matrix representation. This algorithm uses the same process of encoding and decoding as that of decimal matrix code. The algorithms use vector adjustment, S={S,32'b0} for most significant bit data correction and S={32'b0,S} for least significant bit data correction, for a correction capability of maximum of 31 adjacent bits out of 64 data bits.

```

Inputs: Enable, datain
Outputs: H, V
If Enable = 1 then
    H[8:0] = datain[7:0] + datain[23:16]
    H[17:9] = datain[15:8] + datain[31:24]
    H[26:18] = datain[39:32] + datain[55:48]
    H[35:27] = datain[47:41] + datain[63:56]
    Vi = dataini ⊕ dataini+32 where i = 0,1, ...,31
Else
    H = 0 and V = 0

Inputs: Enable, H, V, dataread
Output: dataout
If Enable = 1 then
    HD[8:0] = dataread[7:0] + dataread[23:16]
    HD[17:9] = dataread[15:8] + dataread[31:24]
    HD[26:18] = dataread[39:32] + dataread[55:48]
    HD[35:27] = dataread[47:41] + dataread[63:56]
    VDi = datareadi ⊕ datareadi+32 where i = 0,1, ...,31
Syndrome Calculation
    Hdifff = HD ⊕ H
    S = VD ⊕ V
Error Location and Correction
    If Hdifff = 0 and S = 0 then
        dataout = dataread
    Else
        dataout = dataread ⊕ S
Else
    dataout = 0
    
```

(a) (b)

Figure 5. Optimal parity code-1: (a) encoder and (b) decoder

proposed codes occupy a minimum of 118 to a maximum of 175 slice look-up tables i.e., the area utilization is reduced by atleast 32.2% to 54.28% for decoder.

From Figure 12, among all the codes, optimal parity code-4 utilises power delay product of 435.74 pWs while the other existing and proposed codes use a minimum of 403.44 pWs to a maximum of 671.4 pWs i.e., the power delay product is reduced by atleast -8% to 35.09% for encoder. Similarly, the optimal parity code-4 utilises power delay product of 736.28 pWs while the other existing and proposed codes use a minimum of 763.28 pWs to a maximum of 1115.86 pWs i.e., the power delay product is reduced by atleast 3.53% to 34.01% for decoder. Hence the optimal code-4 proves to be best among the codes mentioned for error detection and correction especially when large number of bits get damaged and need repair from memory or equivalent device within very less time. These are well suited for image or video processing applications.

Figure 10. Codes comparison for code rate and bit overhead

Figure 11. Codes comparison for area

Figure 12. Codes comparison for power delay product

4. CONCLUSION

The embedded memories used in highly sensitive applications are usually error prone devices due to congestion at nanometer technologies exposed to radiation effects. During read operation operating at rated clock frequency multiple bit upsets happen and they exhibit as soft errors, then the error detection and correction codes are used to overcome them. The proposed codes are aimed to increase the code rate by using fewer bits overhead. These are capable of correcting at most $(N/2)-1$ adjacent errors in N bit data. The verilog hardware description language coded designs are verified in Xilinx tool for 28nm zynq field programmable gate array. From results obtained, among all the codes mentioned, the optimal code-4 proves to be efficient with 65.3% code rate and only 53.125% bit overhead, atleast 21.05% and 32.2% less area utilization for encoder and decoder respectively. Also it uses atleast 3.53% and 34.01% less power delay product for its encoder and decoder respectively. Further these codes can incorporate low power techniques for faster operation and optimized area.

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